

PRONOUNS IN LAIRAMLO

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Abstract- Lairamlo is the name of the dialect of Tangkhul. Tangkhul is one of the tribal languages of Manipur which belongs to the Kuki-Chin-Naga subgroup of the Tibeto-Burman subfamily of languages (Grierson's LSI, 1903). Lairamlo is spoken by the Ringpam people in Ringpam village or Momlo Ringpam village in the Machi sub-division of the Tengnoupal district of Manipur.

The present paper is an attempt to describe the morpho-syntactic aspects of the pronoun of Lairamlo. The dialect has no gender distinction in the case of first-person and second-person personal pronouns but gender distinction is made in the case of third personal pronouns in Lairamlo i.e., *imiŋ* for 'he' and *inuŋ* for 'she'. Pronouns in Lairamlo can be categorized into the following types: i) personal pronouns, ii) demonstrative pronouns, iii) interrogative pronouns, iv) reflexive pronouns and v) indefinite pronouns. Reflexive pronouns in Lairamlo are formed by the suffixing *-t^hra* for singular and *-nəniŋ* for plural to the personal pronoun. The data are collected from Ringpam village of Tengnoupal district of Manipur through questionnaire and interview methods. The sources of data for this research are primary and secondary. The secondary source includes the available written materials like books, journals, articles etc. The primary source is mainly based on speech data of the community. The data collection was done through personal contact with informants of different sexes, professionals and age groups. The data is cross-checked with the other speakers of the same dialect for authenticity and consistency of the same.

Keywords: Pronouns, Lairamlo, Tangkhul, Ringpam, Manipur.

1. INTRODUCTION

Lairamlo is a dialect of Tangkhul, which belongs to the Kuki-Chin-Naga subgroup of the Tibeto-Burman sub-family of languages (Grierson's LSI, 1903). Tangkhul has many dialects. Arokianathan (1987) noted that there are 219 Tangkhul villages and each village has its own dialect or speech form named after the village. Besides, Mortensen (2003) made a similar statement that Tangkhuls are quite diversified linguistically, and the speech varieties of most of the Tangkhul villages are not mutually intelligible with those of neighbouring villages (though the similarities are large enough to facilitate the rapid learning of one another's languages). Lairamlo is also one of the dialects of Tangkhul, which is spoken by the Ringpam people in Ringpam village or Momlo Ringpam village in the Machi sub-division of Chandel District of Manipur. According to the 2011 census, Ringpam has 97 households with a total of 440 people of which 211 are male and 229 are female. The dialects do not have their own script or writing system to write their language. Hence, they used Roman script to write their language with some modifications.

2. Typological Features of Lairamlo

- Typologically, Lairamlo is a tonal and agglutinating dialect of Tangkhul.
- Like many other Tibeto-Burman languages, tense is not prominent in Lairamlo So, aspect is commonly an important representation of time in Lairamlo.
- Lairamlo has no grammatical gender. Gender is realized as masculine or feminine based on natural sex. All the male comes under masculine and the female comes under feminine. All the inanimate objects come under the neuter gender.
- The numeral system of Lairamlo is of decimal type.
- Verbs in Lairamlo are not marked for persons, numbers and genders.
- Like many other Tibeto-Burman languages/dialects, the dialect lacks the aspirated voiced velar stops *b^h*, *d^h*, and *g^h*.
- Lairamlo has inclusive-exclusive distinction only in the case of the first-person plural pronoun */a-həntel/* 'we' (inclusive) vs. */i-həntel/* 'we' (exclusive).

3. Objectives

The main objective of the study is to describe the pronoun in Lairamlo, a Kuki-Chin-Naga language mainly spoken in Ringpam village of Tengnoupal district of Manipur.

4. Methodology

The method for collecting data for the study includes both primary and secondary sources. The primary source is mainly based on the speech of the community. The data collection was done through personal contact with informants

of different sexes, professionals and age groups of the community. The data is cross-checked with the other speakers of the same dialect for authenticity and consistency of the same. The secondary method includes the available written materials like books, journals, articles etc.

5. Pronouns in Lairamlo

Pronoun can be used in all persons whereas a noun is always used in the third person. Lairamlo has no gender distinction is made in the case of first and second-person personal pronouns but gender distinction is made in the case of third personal pronoun in Lairamlo i.e., *imiŋ* for 'he' and *inuŋ* for 'she'. Pronouns in Lairamlo can be categorized in the following types:

- (a) Personal pronoun
- (b) Demonstrative pronoun
- (c) Interrogative pronoun
- (d) Reflexive pronoun and
- (e) Indefinite pronoun

5.1. Personal Pronoun

Personal pronoun in Lairamlo can be distinguished in three ways i) first person ii) second person and iii) third person. Both the dialects distinguish three persons and two numbers. Structurally, out of three personal pronouns, first and second personal pronouns are monosyllabic and the third one is bi-syllabic in Lairamlo. It is interesting to note that the second person personal pronoun *nəŋ* seems to be Proto Tibeto-Burman **naŋ* (Benedict 1972). It is also worth mentioning here that the first and second- persons plural are formed by suffixing *-hənte* and the third person plural are formed by suffixing *-hente* as illustrated in the following table:

Table No. 1: Personal pronouns in Lairamlo

Person	Singular		Plural	
	Lairamlo	Gloss	Laramlo	Gloss
First person	<i>a</i>	'I'	<i>ahənte</i> (INCL) <i>ihənte</i> (EXCL)	'we'
Second person	<i>nəŋ</i>	'you'	<i>nəhənte</i>	'you'
Third person	<i>imiŋ/inuŋ/</i>	'he/she'	<i>ihente</i>	'they'

Personal pronouns in the sentence construction in Lairamlo are shown in the following examples:

5.1.1. *ahənte wit-to waŋ-əm-e*
We (INCL) here-LOC come-PROG -DECL
We (including me) are coming here

5.1.2. *ihənte wit-to waŋ-əm-e*
We (EXCL) here-LOC come-PROG -DECL
We (excluding me) are coming here

5.1.3. *a-ne ute-we k^hə-mei-we*
I-NOM bird-ACC NMZ-see-DECL
'I see the bird'

5.1.4. *nəŋ-ne ute-we k^hə-mei-we*
you-NOM bird-ACC NMZ-see-DECL
'You (sg) see the bird'

5.1.5. *imiŋ-ne ute-we k^hə-mei-we*
he-NOM bird-ACC NMZ-see-DECL
'He sees the bird'

5.1.6. *inuŋ-ne ute-we k^hə-mei-we*
she-NOM bird-ACC NMZ-see-DECL
'She sees the bird'

5.2. Demonstrative

A demonstrative pronoun is a determiner that acts as a modifier to a noun or noun phrase. Lairamlo exhibits two types of demonstrative pronouns: proximate vs. remote. In Lairamlo, *heve*, *hi* and *ewe* denote proximate and remote respectively.

Proximate

5.2.1. *heve awe* *ink^huyen-ve*
 DEM 1SG-GEN garden-COP
 ‘This is my garden.’

5.2.2. *hi t̄arot k̄a-p^hre*
 DEM story NMZ-be good
 ‘This good story’

Remote

5.2.3. *ewe fei-we*
 REM-DEM cow-DECL
 ‘That is a cow’

5.3. Interrogative

Interrogative pronouns are used for asking questions. It can be of a person, object, time, manner and quantity. The interrogative pronouns in Lairamlo can be classified into two (i) basic and (ii) derived.

(i) Basic interrogative

The basic interrogative pronouns in Lairamlo are underived ones which means it can stand alone.

ti ‘what’
t^hu ‘who’

k^hutyəŋ ‘how’

(ii) Derived Interrogative

In Lairamlo the derived interrogative pronouns are derived from the basic ones by adding suffixes *pe*, *l̄ə*, *to*, *lo* and *we*. The morpheme *pe* is a male gender marker and the morpheme *l̄ə*, is a question marker and the morpheme *to*, *lo* and *we* are the case marker that is added to the basic interrogative to form derived interrogative. The derived interrogative pronouns in the Lairamlo are:

k^hutyəŋ-do ‘when’
tipe ‘which’
til̄ə ‘why’
tito ‘where’
t^hulo ‘whom’
t^huwe ‘whose’ etc.

Interrogative pronouns in the sentence construction in Lairamlo are shown in the following examples:

5.3.1. *nəŋ ti k̄ə-č̄e-l̄ə*
 you what NMZ-eat-Q
 ‘What do you eat?’

5.3.2. *nəŋ puŋ k^hutyəŋ-do t^hole-əm-l̄ə*
 you time how-LOC get-PROG-Q
 ‘When do you get up?’

5.3.3. *ewe fei-we t^hu-we-le*
 DEM cow-DET who-GEN-Q
 ‘Whose cow is that?’

5.4. Reflexive

Lairamlo reflexive pronoun has a different form for singular and plural. Reflexive pronouns in Lairamlo are formed by the suffixing *-t^hra* for singular and *-nəniŋ* for plural to the personal pronoun. On the other hand, the morpheme *t^hra* is used to mark a singular form and the *nəniŋ* morpheme is used to mark a plural form. Hence, these two grammatical categories are significant in differentiating singular and plural forms of words; examples are shown in the following table.

Table No. 2: Reflexive pronouns in Lairamlo

Person	Singular		Plural	
	Lairamlo	Gloss	Lairamlo	Gloss
1 st person	<i>a-t^hra</i>	‘myself’	<i>h̄ante-nəniŋ</i>	‘ourselves’
2 nd person	<i>n̄ə-t^hra</i>	‘yourself’	<i>n̄əh̄ante-nəniŋ</i>	‘yourselves’
3 rd prson	<i>imiŋ-t^hra</i> <i>inuŋ-t^hra</i>	‘himself/ ‘herself’	<i>ihente-nəniŋ</i>	‘themselves’

5.5. Indefinite

Most of the Tibeto-Burman languages do not have a distinct form of indefinite pronouns. But, in Lairamlo, some of the indefinite pronouns have distinct forms as shown in the following examples.

Lairamlo	Gloss
<i>kədiŋ</i>	‘nothing / none’
<i>həmp^həŋp^həŋ</i>	‘anything’
<i>əcəm</i>	‘sometime’

Some of the indefinite pronouns in the Lairamlo are formed by using compounding. Like many other Tibeto-Burman languages, Lairamlo does not have a distinct form in some cases of indefinite pronouns. The structure of compound indefinite pronouns in Lairamlo is illustrated in the following examples:

<i>t^hu-le-hət</i>	‘anyone’
Who-and-NUM	
<i>ti-le-k^hət</i>	‘something’
What-and-NUM	
<i>t^hu-lo-k^hət</i>	‘someone’
Who-and-NUM	

6. Conclusion

Lairamlo is a dialect spoken by the people of a remote area of Manipur state in India. Being a dialect of indigenous people of North-east India, this dialect has a rich heritage and offers a wide scope to explore multi-dimensional socio-cultural phenomena. For instance, the study of pronouns in the Lairamlo dialect found that there is no gender distinction in 1st person and 2nd person pronouns but gender distinction is made in the case of only third-person personal singular pronouns such as *imiŋ* ‘he’ and *inuŋ* ‘she’. Like many other Tibeto-Burman languages, Lairamlo has inclusive-exclusive distinction only in the case of the first-person plural pronoun /*a-hənte/* ‘we’ (inclusive) vs. /*i-hənte/* ‘we’ (exclusive). Pronouns in Lairamlo can be categorized into five types, they are- i) personal pronouns, ii) demonstrative pronouns, iii) interrogative pronouns, iv) reflexive pronouns and v) indefinite pronouns. Reflexive pronouns in Lairamlo are formed by the suffixing *-t^hra* for singular and *-nəniŋ* for plural to the personal pronoun.

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